

Chemical Examination of the Seeds of *Grewia populifolia* Vahl.

S. N. Ganguly, A. K. Bhattacharya, and G. Ganguli

The bark of *Grewia populifolia* Vahl. (Fam. Tiliaceae) is used to clean the hair of vermin¹. Sarkar and Khanna² reported the presence of several amino-acids, sterols, and triterpenes in the plant material. According to them, the bark also possesses pesticidal properties and is used by North Indians for the treatment of tuberculosis. This prompted us to a chemical investigation of the seeds of this plant.

Procedure.—Air-dried, finely ground seeds (500 g.) of *G. populifolia* were successively Soxhletted with petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) and chloroform, each for 40 hr. The residue (0.8 g.) on removal of the solvent from the petroleum extract was taken in ether and washed with cold 5% aqueous NaOH solution to remove some undesirable resinous matter. The alkali-washed ether solution was shaken with water and dried. Distillation of the solvent yielded a gummy residue (5 g.). It was dissolved in benzene (20 ml) and chromatographed over Brockmann alumina (250 g.), using petroleum (b.p. 60-80°), benzene, different mixtures of benzene-chloroform, and chloroform as the successive eluents.

The petroleum and early benzene eluates afforded much oil, whereas the later benzene eluate provided a solid (10 mg.), crystallised from benzene in needles, m.p. 85°, [α]_D²⁰ ± 0° (CHCl₃). Its analysis agreed with C₃₀H₆₂O ± CH₃ and it showed a peak in its IR spectrum at 3.0 μ, characteristic for hydroxyl. Presence of this function was further substantiated by the preparation of an *O*-acetate, m.p. 09°. These data compared well with those reported³ for *n*-triacontanol, CH₃(CH₂)₂₈CH₂OH, the identity being firmly established from a mass spectrometric examination of our sample. The spectrum registered a molecular ion peak at *m/e* 438 for the compound and revealed a fragmentation pattern expected in accordance with the normal straight-chain structure.

The benzene-chloroform (1:1) eluate furnished 50 mg. of a phytosterol which was crystallised from methanol in flakes, m.p. 138°, [α]_D²⁰ -35° (CHCl₃). This was identified as β-sitosterol by direct comparison with an authentic sample, isolated by Aditya Choudhury and Ganguli⁴.

1. Chopra, Nayyar, and Chopra, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1956, p. 129.
2. *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1959, 18C, 20.
3. Hailbron and Bunbury, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds" Vol. IV, Eyre and Spottiswoode, London, 1953, p. 538.
4. *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, 2, 171.

The chloroform extract of the defatted plant material was freed of the solvent to afford 1 g. of a residue which was dissolved in chloroform (8 ml) and similarly passed through Brockmann alumina (100 g.). The benzene-chloroform (1:1) eluate furnished a solid (25 mg.), m.p. 153-55°. Though this solid was eluted as a homogeneous fraction from the alumina column, it showed a broad diffused band in a T.L.C. plate, indicative of its non-homogeneous character. On repeated chromatography (thrice) over Brockmann alumina, it could be separated into three fractions: (A), m.p. 137°; (B), m.p. 143°; (C), m.p. 167°. Fractions (A) and (C) were identified as β -sitosterol and stigmasterol, respectively, by direct comparison with authentic samples. Fraction B responded to the Burchard-Lieberman test for sterols, but could not be further characterised owing to the extreme paucity of the material.

The mass spectrum of the crude sterol mixture, m.p. 153-55°, substantiated our findings, reported above. The spectrum not only contains molecular ion peaks at m/e 414 (β -sitosterol) and 412 (stigmasterol), but also reveals presence of two other components having molecular weights 400 and 398. From the patterns of their fragmentation, as recorded in the spectrum, these latter compounds are recognised to be the demethyl derivatives of β -sitosterol (i.e. campesterol³) and stigmasterol, respectively. In the light of the above mass spectrometric results, fraction (B), m.p. 143°, isolated by us as described earlier, may well be a mixture of the 24-demethyl derivative of stigmasterol and campesterol.

The chloroform-extracted marc of the plant material was further extracted with methanol, but no crystallisable solid could be isolated from the methanol extract. Our search for any alkaloidal matter in the plant also proved unrewarding.

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